

CONTINUUM MODELING AND FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATION OF INCOMPRESSIBLE DIELECTRIC VISCOELASTIC ACTUATORS AT FINITE STRAINS

Mario Kunzemann^a, Astrid S. Pechstein^a, Alexander Humer^a and Michael Krommer^a

^aInstitute of Technical Mechanics, Johannes Kepler University Linz, Austria.

Email: mario.kunzemann@jku.at

Abstract. Dielectric elastomers, known for their ability to undergo large deformations exceeding 100%, are widely used as actuators in adaptive structures and soft robotics. Within the current contribution, we present a continuum material model that captures the incompressibility and viscous behavior of these polymers under finite strain and electric actuation. To address large deformations, we use a multiplicative decomposition of the deformation gradient to separate elastic and viscous effects. The elastic response is represented by a Yeoh potential, which is well suited to describe the material behavior under large strains. The evolution of internal strains is modeled using a dissipation function. Electric field and dielectric displacement are modeled in spatial configuration, leading to an electromechanically coupled problem. We propose a mixed finite element formulation within a variational framework based on the above thermodynamic principles. We introduce a novel approach using volume-preserving tensor-valued elements for internal strains, where we make use of matrix exponential functions to achieve incompressibility exactly. As an example, we consider an experimental setup of a three-dimensional circular actuator. We provide material parameters for VHB4910 for the proposed model, and compare our results to experimental data from a different work.

Keywords: electromechanical coupling, electro-active polymers, viscoelasticity

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to their ability to undergo significant deformations exceeding 100%, dielectric elastomers are frequently used as actuators in adaptive structures or soft robotics applications. In this contribution, we provide a phenomenological continuum material model respecting the nearly incompressible nature of these polymers as well as their viscous characteristics at finite strain in a coupled electro-mechanic setting. Regarding applications there is a great need in the field of soft robotics but also in the area of sensor development. We cite Guo [5] and O'Halloran [12], both of which provide a comprehensive overview concerning the application of such dielectric elastomers. As mentioned in Wissler [13], it is of high interest to predict the behavior of such dielectric elastomers. In many cases only analytic models using linear or non-linear elastic characteristics have been proposed for strongly simplified problem setups, often neglecting three-dimensional effects or the viscoelastic behavior.

For the basic concepts of modeling such large-deformation electro-elastic materials, we cite the comprehensive monograph by Maugin [8] and the more recent review article by Dorfmann and Ogden [4]. Ask et al. [1] provide a phenomenological material model for electrostrictive viscoelastic polymers at finite strain. Kunzemann et al. [7] developed a similar thermodynamically consistent model

for incompressible viscoelastic polymers, which is suitable for finite element discretization. Within this framework, we develop a phenomenological material model for nearly incompressible, dielectric, viscoelastic polymers. To address large deformations, we apply a multiplicative decomposition of the deformation gradient to differentiate between elastic and viscous effects (cf. [1]). The elastic response is modeled using a Yeoh potential. Various intermediate configurations represent the subsystems of a classical linear Wiechert model in the current setting of finite strains. Viscoelastic dissipation is captured through a dedicated dissipation function, which ensures that the Clausius-Duhem inequality is respected locally. Thus, the material model is considered thermodynamically consistent. Electric quantities and electrostatic field equations must be considered with respect to the actual spatial configuration of the body, which results in an electromechanically coupled problem.

We introduce a mixed finite element formulation that incorporates these aspects within a variational framework. In many finite element methods, elastic deformation is modeled using classical or advanced linear or quadratic elements, while viscous strains are represented at integration points. We propose a different approach that employs independent tensor-valued elements for internal strains. Discretizing these internal strains is challenging due to their volume-preserving nature. We use matrix exponential functions to achieve an exactly volume-preserving representation of these strains in our finite element method.

As an example, we consider a three-dimensional model of a circular actuator that was first described in [13]. The acrylic elastomer VHB4910 is used as base material, where the necessary material parameters were determined in the original reference [13]. A comparison to measurements and simulation results provided there is established.

2 CONSTITUTIVE MODEL FOR DIELECTRIC VISCOELASTIC SOLIDS

In this present work a body \mathcal{B} made of viscoelastic and dielectric material is considered. In the undeformed reference configuration, let \mathbf{X} be the coordinates of any material point \mathcal{P} . Under deformation, we denote \mathbf{x} as the spatial coordinates of \mathcal{P} , and $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{X}$ as the displacement field. The deformation gradient is defined in the standard way as $\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{I} + \text{Grad } \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{I} + \partial \mathbf{u} / \partial \mathbf{X}$. Here and in the following, uppercase differential operators such as the gradient Grad, rotation Curl and divergence Div indicate derivation with respect to material coordinates \mathbf{X} , whereas lowercase operators, like grad, curl, and div describe derivatives with respect to spatial coordinates \mathbf{x} . The Jacobi determinant $J = \det \mathbf{F}$ represents the change of volume during deformation.

It is common to split the deformation gradient into its volumetric and isochoric parts, especially for incompressible or nearly incompressible materials. In this context, isochoric quantities will be labeled with a hat symbol, $\mathbf{F} = J^{1/3} \hat{\mathbf{F}}$. To form the constitutive equations we additionally need the right Cauchy-Green tensor \mathbf{C} and its isochoric part $\hat{\mathbf{C}}$, defined by,

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{F}^\top \cdot \mathbf{F}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{C}} = \hat{\mathbf{F}}^\top \cdot \hat{\mathbf{F}} = J^{-2/3} \mathbf{C}. \quad (1)$$

Similar to the work of [1], we decompose the isochoric deformation gradient multiplicatively into an elastic part $\hat{\mathbf{F}}_{e,i}$ and a viscoelastic part $\mathbf{F}_{v,i}$,

$$\hat{\mathbf{F}} = \hat{\mathbf{F}}_{e,i} \cdot \mathbf{F}_{v,i}, \text{ for } i \in \{1, \dots, N\}. \quad (2)$$

With this extension to the classical linear Wiechert model, we have to deal with N independent stress-free, volume-preserving *intermediate* configurations, see e.g. [7]. In our model, the viscoelastic part of

the deformation gradient is assumed to be volume preserving, which implies the kinematic constraint $\det \mathbf{F}_{v,i} \equiv 1$. According to (2), the i^{th} elastic isochoric part of the deformation gradient is given by $\hat{\mathbf{F}}_{e,i} = \hat{\mathbf{F}} \cdot \mathbf{F}_{v,i}^{-1}$ and the corresponding elastic and viscoelastic Cauchy-Green tensors are defined as,

$$\hat{\mathbf{C}}_{e,i} = \hat{\mathbf{F}}_{e,i}^\top \cdot \hat{\mathbf{F}}_{e,i} = \mathbf{F}_{v,i}^{-\top} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{C}} \cdot \mathbf{F}_{v,i}^{-1}, \quad \mathbf{C}_{v,i} = \mathbf{F}_{v,i}^\top \cdot \mathbf{F}_{v,i}. \quad (3)$$

Regarding the actuation, we assume that modeling in electrostatic regime is justified. Here, the electric field \mathbf{e} and the dielectric displacement \mathbf{d} are of interest, which are both regarded as fields in spatial configuration. From Faraday's law, $\text{curl } \mathbf{e} = 0$, we deduce that the electric field \mathbf{e} is a gradient field, meaning that it can be expressed as the negative gradient of the electric potential field ϕ , $\mathbf{e} = -\text{grad } \phi$. Gauss' law implies that the dielectric displacement field \mathbf{d} must be divergence-free in the spatial configuration for non-conducting materials (no free charges), $\text{div } \mathbf{d} = 0$. As a simplification, which can be justified for thin, electroded dielectric structures, the electric field is modeled only in the material, effects from the surrounding air or vacuum are not taken into account, [4]. To transform the above fields from the spatial to the material configuration, we introduce the pull-back of the electric field \mathbf{e} and dielectric displacement \mathbf{d} to their material counterparts, denoted by capital letters,

$$\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{F}^\top \cdot \mathbf{e} = -\text{Grad } \phi, \quad \mathbf{D} = \mathbf{J}\mathbf{F}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{d}. \quad (4)$$

We now develop a thermodynamically consistent model for electroactive viscoelastic materials. Therefore, we define the free energy density Ψ for independent Cauchy-Green tensor \mathbf{C} , viscoelastic tensors $\mathbf{C}_{v,i}$, which will serve as internal variables, and electric field \mathbf{E} . The free energy density is defined additively through several independent potentials: a hyperelastic potential Ψ_∞ describing the long term behavior, viscoelastic energy densities $\Psi_{v,i}$ and a dielectric potential Ψ_{el}^{aug} , which is augmented to include the effect of vacuum permittivity,

$$\Psi(\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{C}_{v,i}, \mathbf{E}) = \Psi_\infty(\mathbf{C}) + \sum_{i=1}^N \Psi_{v,i}(\hat{\mathbf{C}}, \mathbf{C}_{v,i}) + \Psi_{el}^{aug}(\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{E}). \quad (5)$$

We describe the specific choices for the energy densities that make up the augmented free energy Ψ . In this study, the elastic component of the free energy Ψ_∞ will be defined by a nearly incompressible Yeoh hyperelastic potential,

$$\Psi_\infty(\mathbf{C}) = C_{10}^\infty (\text{tr } \mathbf{C} - 3) + C_{20}^\infty (\text{tr } \mathbf{C} - 3)^2 + C_{30}^\infty (\text{tr } \mathbf{C} - 3)^3 + \frac{1}{D_1} (J - 1)^2, \quad (6)$$

with C_{10}^∞ , C_{20}^∞ and C_{30}^∞ being the Yeoh parameters describing the long term behavior and D_1 denoting the compressibility parameter. Concerning the i^{th} multiplicative decomposition, an incompressible Yeoh hyperelastic potential models the elastic energy for $\hat{\mathbf{C}}_{e,i}$ instead. As $\text{tr } \hat{\mathbf{C}}_{e,i} = \hat{\mathbf{C}} : \mathbf{C}_{v,i}^{-1}$, we use the representation,

$$\Psi_{v,i}(\hat{\mathbf{C}}, \mathbf{C}_{v,i}) = C_{10}^{v,i} \left(\hat{\mathbf{C}} : \mathbf{C}_{v,i}^{-1} - 3 \right) + C_{20}^{v,i} \left(\hat{\mathbf{C}} : \mathbf{C}_{v,i}^{-1} - 3 \right)^2 + C_{30}^{v,i} \left(\hat{\mathbf{C}} : \mathbf{C}_{v,i}^{-1} - 3 \right)^3, \quad (7)$$

with $C_{10}^{v,i}$, $C_{20}^{v,i}$ and $C_{30}^{v,i}$ being the Yeoh parameters describing the viscoelastic behavior.

Last, the dielectric potential, represented by Ψ_{el}^{aug} , describes the behavior of polarization within the material. In an isotropic linear dielectric material, this contribution is described by the materials relative electric susceptibility χ . We define Ψ_{el}^{aug} by,

$$\Psi_{el}^{aug}(\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{E}) = -\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 (\chi + J) \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{E}, \quad (8)$$

see also [6]. In this context, ϵ_0 is the permittivity of vacuum.

In order to define the constitutive equations, we use the framework of the Clausius-Duhem inequality, which states the non-negativity of dissipation \mathcal{D} . In the current setting, \mathcal{D} can be described by,

$$\mathcal{D} = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{T} : \dot{\mathbf{C}} - \mathbf{D} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{E}} - \dot{\Psi} \geq 0. \quad (9)$$

In this context, \mathbf{T} is the total second Piola-Kirchhoff stress, \mathbf{D} the material dielectric displacement. Again, $\dot{\mathbf{C}}$, $\dot{\mathbf{E}}$, $\dot{\Psi}$ are each the rate of the right Cauchy-Green tensor, of the electric field and of the augmented free energy. By computing $\dot{\Psi}$ explicitly, equation (9) becomes,

$$\mathcal{D} = - \left(\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{C}} - \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{T} \right) : \dot{\mathbf{C}} - \left(\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{E}} + \mathbf{D} \right) \cdot \dot{\mathbf{E}} - \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{C}_{v,i}} : \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i} \geq 0. \quad (10)$$

Dissipation \mathcal{D} is explicitly defined through the choice of a dissipation function Φ ,

$$\mathcal{D} = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i}} : \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i} \geq 0. \quad (11)$$

This implicitly defines the rate of the viscoelastic Cauchy-Green tensor $\dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i}$ by using the Clausius-Duhem inequality of equation (10). The dissipation function Φ is also composed additively from contributions due to the N internal variables $\mathbf{C}_{v,i}$. To be specific, we use,

$$\Phi = \sum_{i=1}^N \Phi_i(\mathbf{C}_{v,i}, \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i}), \quad \text{with} \quad \Phi_i(\mathbf{C}_{v,i}, \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i}) = \frac{1}{12} \sum_{i=1}^N \eta_i (\mathbf{C}_{v,i}^{-1} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i}) : (\mathbf{C}_{v,i}^{-1} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i}). \quad (12)$$

In the work of Wissler [13], two sets of material parameters are provided. Both contain the Yeoh parameters, C_{10} , C_{20} , C_{30} , defining the instantaneous response, and Prony parameters g_i , τ_i for $N = 4$. Since we base the material characterization on the longterm parameters, these still have to be converted accordingly, same applies to the viscoelastic parts,

$$C_{j0}^\infty = C_{j0} \left(1 - \sum_{i=1}^N g_i \right), \quad C_{j0}^{v,i} = C_{j0} g_i, \quad \text{for } i \in \{1, \dots, N\}, j \in \{1, 2, 3\}. \quad (13)$$

Since there is no further information on the compression parameter D_1 , we define it by Poisson's ratio ν , resulting in,

$$D_1 = \frac{1 - 2\nu}{2C_{10}\nu}. \quad (14)$$

In the dissipation function, each of the terms is governed by a viscosity parameter η_i , which is given by,

$$\eta_i = 6g_i\tau_i C_{10}, \quad \text{for } i \in \{1, \dots, N\}. \quad (15)$$

3 INCREMENTAL MINIMIZATION PRINCIPLE AND FINITE ELEMENTS

In this section, we aim at developing a finite element formulation for viscoelastic solids using an incremental variational formulation. The approach follows a minimization principle, which has been widely employed in the modeling of dissipative processes, including viscoelasticity, as presented by Miehe et al. (cf. [9, 10, 11]). Since the following example can be seen as quasi-static, we do not take the kinetic part into account, also no effects due to gravity will be governed.

For a finite time step $[t_0, t_0 + \Delta t]$ with known initial conditions at time t_0 , we define the *incremental potential* over the time step as:

$$\Pi_t^{t+\Delta t} = \int_{t_0}^{t_0+\Delta t} (\dot{\Psi} + \Phi) dt, \quad (16)$$

where the different terms represent the following energy contributions:

$$\Pi_t^{t+\Delta t} = \underbrace{\Psi_{t_0+\Delta t} - \Psi_{t_0}}_{\text{stored}} + \underbrace{\int_{t_0}^{t_0+\Delta t} \Phi dt}_{\text{dissipated}}. \quad (17)$$

The incremental potential $\Pi_{t_0}^{t_0+\Delta t}$ is then minimized with respect to all admissible displacements and viscoelastic internal variables, while being maximized with respect to the electric field. For a time step size Δt approaching zero, we arrive at,

$$\dot{\Psi} + \Phi \rightarrow \min_{\dot{\mathbf{u}}} \min_{\dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i}} \max_{\dot{\mathbf{E}}}. \quad (18)$$

We can now rewrite equation (18) for the specific choice of the free energy Ψ , resulting in,

$$\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{C}} : \dot{\mathbf{C}} + \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{C}_{v,i}} : \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i} + \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{E}} \cdot \delta \dot{\mathbf{E}} + \Phi \rightarrow \min_{\dot{\mathbf{u}}} \min_{\dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i}} \max_{\dot{\mathbf{E}}}. \quad (19)$$

Variation of the optimization problem (19) yields, for kinematically admissible virtual displacements $\delta \mathbf{u}$, $\delta \mathbf{C}_{v,i}$ and $\delta \mathbf{E}$,

$$\int_{\mathcal{B}} \left(\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{C}} : \delta \mathbf{C} + \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{C}_{v,i}} : \delta \mathbf{C}_{v,i} + \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{E}} \cdot \delta \mathbf{E} \right) dV + \int_{\mathcal{B}} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i}} : \delta \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i} dV = 0. \quad (20)$$

With regard to spatial discretization, we assume $\mathcal{T} = \{T\}$ to be a prismatic triangular finite element mesh of the section of \mathcal{B} . The displacement \mathbf{u} is represented by continuous basis functions $\mathbf{N}_i^{(u)}$ with the approximation order k . The electric potential is also discretized by a continuous basis function with the same order,

$$\mathbf{u} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_u} q_i^{(u)} \mathbf{N}_i^{(u)}, \quad \phi = \sum_{i=1}^{n_\phi} q_i^{(\phi)} \mathbf{N}_i^{(\phi)}. \quad (21)$$

Moreover, kinematic boundary conditions $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0}$ on boundary part Γ_{fix} and also $\phi = \phi_0$ on the electroded boundary Γ_{el} have to be satisfied.

The approximation of the viscoelastic internal variables $\mathbf{C}_{v,i}$ can be achieved by using the viscoelastic strain tensor $\mathbf{S}_{v,i}$ containing the independent viscoelastic strains $s_{i,xx}$, $s_{i,yy}$, $s_{i,xy}$, $s_{i,xz}$ and $s_{i,yz}$. This can be challenging due to their volume-preserving nature. To address this, we use matrix exponential functions to achieve an exact representation of these strains,

$$\mathbf{S}_{v,i} = \begin{bmatrix} s_{i,xx} & s_{i,xy} & s_{i,xz} \\ s_{i,xy} & s_{i,yy} & s_{i,yz} \\ s_{i,xz} & s_{i,yz} & -s_{i,xx} - s_{i,yy} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{C}_{v,i} = \exp(2\mathbf{S}_{v,i}). \quad (22)$$

The viscoelastic strains $s_{i,\alpha\beta}$ are discretized by piecewise polynomials of approximation order $k - 1$, one order less than displacement and electric potential.

Concerning the evaluation of the matrix exponential function, we use a high-order Taylor approximation,

$$\mathbf{C}_{v,i} = \exp(2\mathbf{S}_{v,i}) \simeq \mathbf{I} + 2\mathbf{S}_{v,i} + 2\mathbf{S}_{v,i}^2 + \dots + \frac{2^n}{n!} \mathbf{S}_{v,i}^n, \quad (23)$$

with n the order of the series expansion. In order to handle the occurrence of high viscoelastic strains in the simulation, choosing a high order is necessary. The choice $n = 30$ will prove sufficient in the numerical example. Since the example is considered quasi-static, the rate of the viscoelastic strains is approximated in a backward Euler time-stepping scheme

$$\dot{s}_{i,\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{\Delta t} (s_{i,\alpha\beta}(t + \Delta t) - s_{i,\alpha\beta}(t)). \quad (24)$$

With the rate of the viscoelastic strains $\dot{s}_{i,\alpha\beta}$, the rate of the strain tensor $\dot{\mathbf{S}}_{v,i}$ is provided. The rate of the viscoelastic Cauchy-Green tensor then follows as,

$$\dot{\mathbf{C}}_{v,i} = \text{Sym} \left(2\dot{\mathbf{S}}_{v,i} \exp(2\mathbf{S}_{v,i}) \right). \quad (25)$$

4 COMPUTATIONAL IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULTS

We test our formulation against the measurements provided in the work of Wissler [13]. There, the authors aimed at creating a corresponding model for the acrylic elastomer VHB4910 in a Yeoh and Prony series representation, and to verifying this model for a circular actuator. The characterization was done by performing relaxation and tensile tests with a rectangular specimen with a thickness of 1 mm. For the actuator, a circular specimen was pre-stretched radially up to a radial strain of $s_{pre} = 308\%$, resulting in an outer radius of $R = 75$ mm and a thickness of $t = 0.06$ mm, as seen in Figure 1. This configuration is held in a frame for 1 hour, after which a circular area with $r_0 = 22$ mm is coated with beaten gold on the upper and lower surface to form electrodes. Within 5 seconds, a voltage is applied linearly up to a limit value of 3.5 kV. This voltage is then held constant for a another 175 seconds, which causes the coated surface to expand, as indicated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Circular actuator

Table 1: fitted material parameters.

Parameter	Unit	Wissler [13]	current
C_{10}	MPa	0.0693	0.0693
C_{20}	MPa	-9.88×10^{-4}	-9.88×10^{-4}
C_{30}	MPa	16.7×10^{-6}	16.7×10^{-6}
g_1	-	0.547	0.493
g_2	-	0.198	0.250
g_3	-	0.110	0.0929
g_4	-	0.0384	0.0628
t_1	s	0.135	2.980
t_2	s	0.382	49.462
t_3	s	37.1	299.679
t_4	s	217	5564.668

First, we tried to use the parameters directly in our formulation, and reproduce the measurements from the relaxation tests. As expected, the results did not agree perfectly; in the original work [13] the large deformation viscoelastic model is formulated in a different manner as proposed here. Instead, we used the relaxation test data for the largest nominal strain of 500 % and fitted the viscoelastic parameters g_i and τ_i for our model, while keeping the instantaneous hyperelastic response as characterized though the Yeoh parameters the same. Optimization using a non-linear bounded least squares algorithm leads to the results depicted in Figure 2. The green markers represent the measurements, the orange dashed curve shows the simulation with the original parameters from [13], and the blue curve displays the simulation with the new fitted parameters, which are shown in Table 1 as *current*. The implemented geometry for the finite element analysis can be seen in Figure 3. Due to symmetries, the geometry can be simplified with corresponding boundary conditions on the two faces. The in-plane displacements u_x and u_y are set to zero on these surfaces, respectively. Vertical displacement $u_z = 0$ is prohibited on the bottom circumferential edge, as the sample becomes significantly thinner, whereas the radial displacement is prescribed matching the pre-strain on the circumferential face. To achieve the given pre-stretch $s_{pre} = 3.08$, the initial radius was set to $R_0 = R/(1 + s_{pre})$ resulting in $R_0 = 18.38$ mm. The finite element mesh consists of 212 prismatic triangular elements. Due to the thin structure, two layers of third order prismatic elements are used to prevent locking. This leads to a total of 10731 degrees of freedom for the displacement, 1225 degrees of freedom for the electric field and 76320 degrees of freedom for the viscoelastic strains.

Figure 2: Relaxation experiment

The electrodes were defined circular on the upper and lower surfaces, with pre-stretched radius r_0 . To improve convergence, the electric field is only modeled in the section directly between the electrodes. This simplification is justified mainly due to the thin structure, shown in Figure 4, as no significant electric field is expected in the outer region. In [13], the given electric susceptibility χ is expected to be $\chi = 4.7$. However, in a more recent work [3], the susceptibility of VHB4910 was characterized in large strain regime around $\chi = 4.1$, which we use in our computations. Last, the compression parameter D_1 was defined by using equation (14), using a Poisson's ration of $\nu = 0.44$, which has been characterized by [2].

Figure 3: Circular actuator - Implementation

Figure 4: electric field distribution

To measure the effect of the electric field, the radial expansion at the transition between the electrode and the sample was used. The original radius after pre-stretching r_0 is set in relation to the current radius r_1 to calculate the nominal radial strain,

$$s_r = \frac{r_1}{r_0} - 1. \quad (26)$$

Figure 5: Measured and calculated nominal radial strain

Figure 5 represents the comparison of the nominal radial strain between simulation and measurements. The blue line indicates the numerical results, whereas the measurements are marked in green. The red curve shows the prescribed electric potential over time. The contours of the two results are similar, but there is a noticeable offset. In computations, we see sensitivity with respect to both the choice of the electric susceptibility χ and the Poisson ratio ν .

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